

Seasonal Variations in the Abundance of *Clupeidae*, *Scainidae* and *Mugilidae* in Forcados River Estuary

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Abstract

The Forcados River Estuary, found in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria, is home to numerous economically important fish species, including *Clupeidae* (sardines and herrings), *Sciaenidae* (croakers), and *Mugilidae* (mulletts). However, it has been observed that season has a significant impact on fish fauna composition in the tropics. This study was carried out to determine the seasonal variations in the composition of some economically important fish species in the Forcados River estuary with the aim of understanding the impacts of some environmental variables on their populations. Fish samples were collected between January 2017 and January 2018 using a combination of seine nets, gillnets, and hook-and-line gear. Environmental parameters including salinity, air temperature, pH, and water temperature were also measured. Samples were sorted, classified, and counted in the laboratory. A total of 4511 individuals were collected during the sampling period. During the dry season, a total of 2684 (59%) were recorded. On the other hand, a total of 1827 accounting for 41% were recorded during the wet season. *Mugilidae* dominated the rainy season catch, while the dry season catch was dominated by *Clupeidae* and *Scainidae*. The Forcados River Estuary is rich in fish species with an interesting seasonal twist. The canonical correlation indicated a perfect linear relationship between the first canonical components of the environmental parameters and fish abundance. The t-test revealed significant differences between the data recorded for the dry and wet seasons. Further research along this line is encouraged to improve data reliability and insights, optimal food production, and conservation.

Keywords: Forcados River estuary, Niger Delta, *Clupeid*, *Scainidae*, *Mugilidae*, Seasons.

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Estuaries are highly productive transitional ecosystems that provide essential resources and services for human survival and development; consequently, many communities thrive around these aquatic environments. The Forcados River estuary is no exception, as it accommodates a significant number of communities (Opute, 2000) due to its productive nature within the Niger Delta region, which supports a significant amount of economically and ecologically important

aquatic biodiversity (Opute, 2000; Iwegbue *et al.*, 2018; Ogidiaka and Ikomi, 2021; Ogidiaka *et al.*, 2022).

Among the predominant and economically important fish species in the Forcados River estuary are *Clupeidae*, *Scainidae*, and *Mugilidae* (Ogidiaka and Ikomi, 2021). Clupeids are characterized by distinct body scales that differentiate them from other teleost fishes (Leyli *et al.*, 2020). These fishes are filter feeders that possess diverse groups

of trophic feeders and habitats (Leyli *et al.*, 2020). *Mugilids*, classified as ray-finned fishes, constitute a critical nutritional resource for many coastal communities in Nigeria (Ogidiaka and Ikomi, 2021). The genus, commonly referred to as croaker, has been identified as abundant and of economic significance within the aquatic ecosystems in Nigeria (Isangedighi, 2001; Ogidiaka and Ikomi, 2021).

A good understanding of the seasonal variation in fish abundance is essential for both biodiversity conservation and the formulation of effective management strategies (Costa *et al.*, 2018). One of the primary aims of fish community ecology is to identify seasonal variations in species relative abundance, a subject of considerable research interest (Castillo-Rivera, 2013). Previous studies conducted on the estuary include works by Ogidiaka and Ikomi (2021) and Ogidiaka *et al.* (2022). However, none of these studies have compared the seasonal catch of these ecologically significant species in relation to various environmental parameters. Thus, the objective of this study was to assess the seasonal variations in the predominant fish species in the Forcados River Estuary.

This study seeks to address the existing gap in knowledge regarding the seasonal dynamics of fish abundance in the Forcados River estuary, Nigeria, which is crucial for effective conservation, responsible fishing practices, and the optimal use of fish resources. Despite the ecological and economic significance of fish species in estuaries, threats such as climate change, pollution, and overfishing jeopardize their long-term sustainability, the livelihoods of dependent communities, and the food security of Nigeria. This study investigated the seasonal variations in the abundance of *Clupeidae*, *Sciaenidae*, and *Mugilidae*, while

analyzing the relationships between environmental factors (pH, temperature, salinity) and seasonal dynamics to inform evidence-based policies, conservation measures, and sustainable fishing practices, ultimately ensuring the continuous contribution of the estuary to Nigeria's economy and food security.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Description of study area

The Forcados River estuary is located between latitudes 5°21' to 5°35' N and longitude 5°3' to 5°51' E. The geographical area studied experiences two predominant climatic seasons, namely the wet and dry season. The rainy season lasts from April to November, whereas the dry season spans from the month of November to March.

2.2 Sample collection/Laboratory studies

Air temperature, water temperature, salinity, and pH were measured using standard methods. Fish samples were collected from January 2017 to January 2018 using a combination of seine nets, gillnets, and hook-and-line gear. Fish samples were collected from artisanal fishers during the same timeframe. The samples were sorted, classified, counted, and labelled in appropriate plastic containers using fish identification keys according to Idodo-Umeh (2003) and Olaosebikan and Raji (2013).

3.0 RESULTS

Table 1 shows the seasonal variations in the number of individual species. A noticeable trend of increased catches during the dry season was observed. Throughout the sampling period, a total of 4,511 individuals were collected. During the dry season, 2,684 individuals representing 59% were captured. Conversely, during the wet season, a total of 1,827 individuals, which accounted for 41% were recorded.

Table 1: Seasonal variation in the number of individuals of fish captured.

S/N	Family/Species	Total Abundance	Dry Season	Rainy Season
1	<i>Ethmalosa fimbriata</i>	983	605	378
2	<i>Ilisha africana</i>	621	472	149
4	<i>Pseudotolithus elongatus</i>	860	663	197
5	<i>Pseudotolithus senegalensis</i>	690	480	210
6	<i>Liza falcipinnis</i>	870	260	610
7	<i>Liza gradisquamis</i>	275	125	150
8	<i>Mugil liza</i>	22	11	11
9	<i>Mugil cephalus</i>	190	68	122
	Total	4511	2684	1827
	Percentage		59.0	41.0

Mugilidae constituted the majority of the catch during the rainy season, as depicted in figure 1, whereas the dry season catch was

primarily dominated by *clupeidae* and *scainidae*.

Figure 1: Percentage of the individual species caught seasonally during the study period.

The *Clupeidae* family showed a greater abundance throughout the dry season (Figure 2). A comparable pattern was observed in the *scianidae* family, while *mugilidae* demonstrated a higher abundance in the rainy season throughout the study period.

3.1 Canonical correlations

The canonical correlation analysis revealed a perfect linear relationship between the first canonical components of the environmental parameters and fish abundance.

Figure 2: Seasonal variation in the abundance of the three dominant families in Forcados river estuary.

Figure 3: Canonical components of the environmental parameters and fish abundance.

3.2 Observations in canonical coefficients

In terms of environmental parameters, air temperature, water temperature and salinity had positive contributions, while pH had a

negative impact on the first component. *Mugilidae* demonstrated a positive contribution to fish abundance, whereas *Scainidae* and *Clupeidae* showed negative

contributions to the first component (Tables 2a and 2b).

Table 2a: Canonical coefficients for environmental parameters (x)

Parameters	Component 1	Component 2
Air Temp	0.5	0.0
Water Temp	0.5	0.0
Salinity	0.5	0.0
pH	-0.5	0.0

Table 2b: For fish species (y)

Parameters	Component 1	Component 2
<i>Mugilidae</i>	0.577	0.0
<i>Scainidae</i>	-0.577	0.0
<i>Clupeidae</i>	-0.577	0.0

The biplot represents the relationship between environmental parameters (indicated by the blue arrows) and fish abundance (depicted by orange arrows) along the first component (Figure 4). For the environmental parameters, air temperature, water temperature, and salinity aligned in

the same direction, signifying positive contribution to the canonical component, whereas pH pointed in the opposite direction, indicating a negative contribution. For fish abundance, *mugilidae* had a positive contribution to the canonical component, whereas *Scainidae*, and *Clupeidae* had negative contributions. The direction and length of the arrows illustrated the orientation and strength of their effects respectively. This visualization helped to understand how environmental parameters correlated with fish abundance patterns.

The permutation test shown above for the CCA produced the following results: 0.91, 0.91, 0.91 (Figure 5). These results indicated that the correlation observed in the data was statistically significant at 0.01 levels, indicating that the relationship between environmental parameters and fish species in the dataset was unlikely to have occurred by chance.

From the analysis (Table 3), both one-tailed and two-tailed t-tests indicated that the results were statistically significant.

Figure 4: CCA biplot illustrates the relationship between the environmental parameters (blue arrows) and fish abundance (orange arrows)

Figure 5: Permutation test for the CCA

Table 3: t-Test paired two samples for means of species abundance

	Dry Season	Wet Season
Mean	335.5	228.375
Variance	63752.28571	34336.83929
Observations	8	8
Pearson Correlation	0.315218284	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
df	7	
t Stat	1.156902849	
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.142630935	
t Critical one-tail	1.894578604	
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.285261871	
t Critical two-tail	2.364624251	

p>0.05

3.3 Seasonal variation in environmental parameters observed from the plots

i. Scatter plot of environmental parameters: During the dry season, both air and water temperatures were slightly lower than those observed in the wet season. Salinity levels were marginally reduced, indicating a lower concentration of dissolved

salt in the water. The pH values were slightly elevated compared to those in the wet season. During the wet season, the increase in air and water temperatures was likely attributed to climatic conditions. Additionally, higher salinity was also observed, potentially due to the reduced dilution of water sources by rainfall, while

lower pH levels were recorded, indicating increased acidity during this period. The results showed that seasonal variations in environmental parameters had a direct impact on the aquatic ecosystems (Figure 6).

ii. Scatter plot of fish species: During the wet season, *Mugilidae* experienced a significant rise in population compared to the dry season, while population of *Scainidae* and *Clupeidae* saw a decline, with *Clupeidae* experiencing the most significant reduction.

During the dry season, counts for *Scainidae* and *Clupeidae* were higher compared to those of *Mugilidae*. The results revealed that the *Mugilidae* population was the smallest among the three species. This analysis revealed that the distribution and abundance of fish species were significantly shaped by seasonal environmental variations. *Mugilidae* appeared to flourish better in wet conditions, whereas *Scainidae* and *Clupeidae* were more adapted to the parameters observed during the dry season.

Figure 6: Seasonal variation in environmental parameters observed from the plots

3.4 Biplot analysis

i. Environmental parameters (blue arrows): Physical parameters including air and water temperatures exhibited a positive correlation with fish species during the wet season (*Mugilidae*). Salinity and pH exhibited distinct influences on the distribution of species (figure 7).

ii. Fish species (green arrows): *Clupeidae* and *Scainidae* were closely correlated, as observed in the dry season, due to lower salinity and pH. Conversely, *Mugilidae*

demonstrated a more significant association with the conditions prevalent in the wet season (higher salinity and acidity).

The biplot revealed the influence of environmental parameters on species abundance and distribution. The analysis highlighted significant impacts on salinity and water temperature. It was found that *Mugilidae* thrived more effectively in the wet season, as indicated by the measured parameter values. Furthermore, *Clupeidae* and *Scainidae* exhibited better adaptation to the conditions observed during the dry season compared to those in the wet season.

Figure 7: Seasonal variations between environmental variables and fish species

4.0 DISCUSSION

The substantial quantity of fish captured indicates a clear instance of resource partitioning, where various fish species effectively utilized the available resources in the aquatic environment across both seasons. The findings revealed that the catch during the dry season surpassed that of the wet seasons. This may be attributed to the more stable environmental conditions associated with the dry season. The rainy season is usually associated with an influx of waste/turbid water, leading to fluctuating levels of dissolved oxygen, salinity, and nutrients. The increased abundance of clupeids recorded during the dry season aligns with the observations made by Udo and Bassey (2017) in the Cross River estuary. This was further supported by the observed catch of *E. Ethmalosa* off the Aiyetoro Coast during the dry months as reported by Kusemiju and Onadeko, (1990).

The wet season appeared to favour the abundance of *Mugilidae*, which agrees with the findings reported by Udo and Bassey

(2017). This could be attributed to the availability of food during the rainy season. In addition, the large volumes of water during the wet season are characterized by restricted movement, making many fish less susceptible to capture (Offem *et al.*, 2011). Thus, it is possible to increase fish abundance when targeting them strategically. Four species (*L. falcipinnis*, *L. grandisquamis*, *Mugilcephalus* and *M. Liza*) (*Liza dumerili*, *L. falcipinnis*, *L. grandisquamis*, *Mugilcephalus* and *M. curema*) were reported caught in the Lagos lagoon during the dry season from December 2007 to March 2008, as noted by Soyinka and Adekoya, (2011).

Species count was primarily dominated by *L. falcipinnis*, which contrasts with the reports identifying *Liza dumerili* as the most abundant in the Lagos Lagoon, as documented by Soyinka and Adekoya (2011). Seasonal variations in fish species abundance within subtropical and tropical estuaries have been linked with changes in rainfall patterns (Castillo-Rivera, 2002; Meynecke, 2006) and the inflow of freshwater (Kimmerer, 2002; Tsou and

Matheson, 2002; Young and Potter, 2002). Additionally, water quality factors, such as salinity and turbidity, significantly impacted on fish composition and distribution, with their concentrations being influenced by seasonal rainfall patterns (Blaber, 1995; Martino and Able, 2003; Barletta *et al.*, 2005). Temperature has been identified as another important factor that significantly influences the seasonal composition and abundance of fish species in estuaries (Harrison and Whitfield, 2006; James *et al.*, 2013).

The considerable seasonal variations observed in the abundance of these species can be attributed to a combination of environmental factors including temperature, pH, salinity, nutrient availability, predation, and food supply. This was further validated by the chart produced from the canonical correspondence analysis.

5.0 CONCLUSION

This study assessed the seasonal variations in the abundance of clupeids *Sciaenidae* and *Mugilidae* in Forcados River estuary in Nigeria. The findings revealed significant seasonal variations, with *Clupeidae* and *Sciaenidae* predominating during the dry season while *Mugilidae* dominated the wet season.

This study highlights the rich fish biodiversity of the estuary and emphasized the importance of understanding seasonal dynamics for effective conservation and sustainable fishing practices. The findings from this study will inform fisheries management and enhance fish production in order to bolster food security in the country.

To ensure long-term sustainability, it is advised to conduct regular monitoring of fish populations, implement seasonal closures or gear restrictions, adopt ecosystem-based fisheries management, and encourage sustainable fishing practices. Implementing these recommendations will help protect the estuary fish resources, support local communities, and enhance food security in Nigeria.

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8.0 CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

9.0 AUTHORS' CONTRIBUTIONS

Ogidiaka-Obende, E., was responsible for project conceptualization and design; Ogidiaka-Obende, E.; Atadiose, J. handled data collection. Ndinwa, G.C.C. conducted data/statistical analysis, while Ndinwa, G.C.C., Anayeokwu, S.N., Oduma, E.O., Omoarebun, E.O., Ugegeh D. O., Atadiose, J., and Anigboro F.O. collaborated in drafting the manuscript, manuscript review and editing, and finalization of the manuscript.

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